

Anchoring the Image of the Sea: Copying, Coastlines, and the Manuscript Nautical Chart of the Late Medieval to Early Modern Period

Abstract: The birth of the nautical chart in the late medieval period was a watershed moment in the history of cartography. So far, however, the artisanal practices permitting the stunning subsequent proliferation of sea charts have remained poorly-understood, and little evidence on extant charts has been recovered. This paper systematically explores the techniques enabling the copying of manuscript sea charts' coastlines from the fourteenth to early seventeenth centuries, bringing attention to the ways these processes both shaped and reveal the late medieval and early modern understanding of the Mediterranean. By reframing nautical charts in terms of their characteristics as drawings, placing mapmaking in a broader context of two-dimensional graphic arts, and making careful use of an ever-growing corpus of high-resolution digital reproductions, new insights into chartmakers' changing approaches to the transmission of geographical information are offered, and directions for further research opened.

Keywords: Nautical cartography, manuscript maps, copying, pouncing, carbon transfer, stencils, squaring grid, pantograph, drawing, map production, art history, visual culture

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Introduction

This text aims to give voice to the myriad artisanal processes that enabled the handing-down of hard-won images of the Mediterranean (and later, the wider waters of the world) during the heyday of manuscript chart production. The nautical chart emerged in the thirteenth century and reflected contemporary navigational practices based on compass courses and estimated distances; from its earliest incarnations, the nautical chart's graphical content reflects mariners' concerns. While other means of navigating the Mediterranean waters flourished in the era preceding the chart and compass, once available, charts rapidly became essential on-board equipment supporting ever-intensifying and expanding trade. As is evident in the corpus of surviving works, which skews towards luxurious exemplars, the nautical chart found an audience both on and off of ships. The early establishment of parallel production of navigational and decorative charts is likewise implied in the 1408 letter discussed by Pujades pertaining to the Datini family business, which evaluates a recently-bought chart according to its utility or inutility at sea.¹ But at the center of the burgeoning manuscript chart industry, however intimate its connection to seafaring, we find terrestrial labor: from the late thirteenth to early seventeenth centuries, continuous, intensive nautical chart dissemination relied heavily on the humble labor of routine copying.² The methods adopted for chart copying reflected the nature of these industries, which demanded a consistent product and speedy turnaround. This paper focuses on how cartographers went about copying the *sine qua non* of the chart: its coastlines.³

Despite important investigations into workshop organization,⁴ the nuts and bolts of chart copying remain largely hypothetical. Scholars who have shown curiosity about draftsman-like aspects of chart copying have tended only to look at methods treated in the few extant sixteenth-century texts addressing the matter.⁵ Some laudable engagements with these texts can be found in Tony Campbell's chapter on nautical charts the *History of Cartography* and in Ramon Pujades's *Cartes Portolanes*; although reaching different conclusions, both authors model the circumspection needed when dealing with documentary sources.⁶ Piero Falchetta pushed further by considering the techniques recommended by artist Cennino Cennini in his ca. 1400 *Libro dell'Arte* and looking for signs of production methods in surviving charts.⁷ In his doctoral dissertation, Kevin Sheehan provided an crucial leap forward by replicating the copying procedures listed in sixteenth-century treatises.⁸ Conversely, Laurent Monsaingeon has looked closely at the features of two peculiar charts to provocatively argue the sixteenth-century use of a pantograph.⁹ What is missing so far is a comprehensive survey of historical copying methods used from the turn of the

thirteenth to early seventeenth centuries, and a concerted effort to pin down the evidence these techniques might leave on charts.

Modern over-estimation for innovation, to which even historians can fall prey, has left some of the most prolific nautical chartmakers in an awkward position; a monotonous body of work can eventually strike contemporary observers as a failure of imagination.¹⁰ Having identified any variations in ornament, toponymy, or geographical models, such charts are duly classified and, too often, set aside. But it is in the most repetitive of bodies of work that we are supplied the ideal laboratory for studying the copying process and, ultimately, its rich epistemological insights. Without striving to understand what chartmakers themselves paid attention to while reproducing charts, we are on unsteady ground when attempting to use charts to illustrate contemporary convictions about maritime geography, and we may easily err in assigning explanations to changes in hydrographic representations.

Before going any further, it is worth pausing to bring some order to the concept of copying. We should first note that a copy exists by virtue of its relation to a model, and it is the act of copying that renders a graphic object a model. Because of the spectrum of apparent resemblance between a model and a copy, we might now specify a few types of copying behaviors. Copying may first of all describe the use of one work to *inspire* the appearance of another (we can dub this ‘after-image’ copying, in reference to the lingering mental image of the model exploited by the copyist). The copyist could choose to emulate any number of features in their model, including composition, color scheme, iconography, and ornamental program. After-image copying does not stipulate the presence of the model during the act of replication; it could operate purely on the memory of the copyist. A second sense of the word copy might be applied to replication typified by continuous visual reference to a model and a conscientious effort at strict mimicry (‘copying by eye’);¹¹ picture a person at a table with their model and blank sheet of paper, sparing no effort to create, where it matters, an identical replica.¹² This is a painstaking work; it is a process which might be facilitated by a squaring grid to avoid compounding proportional errors. A last meaning of copying, and the chief subject of this paper, is that activity in which the model and copy are ‘bridged’ by procedures or devices that aim to guarantee conformity across copies, and mitigate cognitive fatigue and time expenditure.¹³

The application of bridged copying methods to manuscript chartmaking is a natural fit. Such reproduction processes gave cartographers confidence that their copies retained the acceptable version of maritime geography embodied in the working model, and, to an extent, allowed people with a less-than-ideal mimetic eye/hand to participate in chart copying. The fact that bridged copying was commonplace in the fine and decorative arts during the same period highlights the labor-intensiveness of copying by eye or

creating *ex nihilo*, and suggests that unrelenting innovation was far from mandatory for these craftsmen. While these points support the plausibility of bridging procedures in chart reproduction, the real proof is found in marks of copying techniques on extant charts, and in the sometimes uncanny similarities of their ink coastlines.

Charts as Drawings

Fruitful inquiry into copying demands that we temporarily shift and narrow our reading of nautical charts, and begin to regard them above all else as a specific kind of *graphic* object. Copying is, after all, a *drawing* problem. The portolan chart is a very peculiar sort of drawing: born at sea, its existence on parchment manifested a constant tension between legibility/simplification and preservation of maritime knowledge tantamount to navigation, trade, and, later, exploration (and on top of that, chartmakers had to satisfy the diverse needs of buyers and maintain a viable business). Since talking about copying means talking about drawings, I will now give an overview of some of the salient graphical features of nautical charts.

The nautical chart is a drawing whose proportions had to either conform to an accepted version of the real configuration of the Mediterranean coasts, or surrender its function (and market) as a seafaring tool. This much is implied by the compass lines (or rhumb lines) and distance scales, which should have at least reminded the cartographer of such standards when they created a new chart. We might, therefore, say that the chart is a drawing in which proportions and spatial relations are semi-inflexible. That is, while certain 'iconographic' aspects of a map can vacillate in scale/trajectory as long as they keep their recognizable form (such as the Gulf of Corinth), nautical chartmakers clearly could not render the entire Mediterranean as a mere pastiche of familiar landmass shapes. Some geometric (or in drawing terms, proportional/spatial) relations had to be respected. Given this precondition, and the difficulty of checking a two-dimensional copy against the actual layout of the Mediterranean experienced by mariners, the copyist was both deeply dependent upon model charts and highly incentivized to find copying methods that ensured all indispensable spatial relations were preserved.

The manuscript nautical chart of the Mediterranean and Black Sea is based on a single, very long line that follows the Atlantic coast south along western France, past Portugal, then (moving clockwise) circumscribes Italy, the Peloponnese, goes up into and around the Black Sea, then down the coasts of Turkey and the Near East, over Egypt, Libya, and the rest of north Africa, and exiting again into the Atlantic past Gibraltar. This line can be broken intermittently by perpendicular lines of variable length and elaboration representing inlets and rivers. In addition, the chart includes closed lines which do not connect

Fundamental line types	
	Serrated
	Crenellated
	Eroded crenellated
	Bitten
	Circular bite (left) and cordiform bite (right)
	Undulating

Figure 1: Fundamental lines on manuscript nautical charts

to each other or to this main long line: the perimeters of islands. Frequently, the islands have a generalized shape and may be arranged in rows or clusters.¹⁴

That fundamental long line is a busy one. But the dizzying exactitude of the drawing on portolan charts is, to some extent, misleading. A rather strict vocabulary of lines and shapes, the use of which varies over time, is employed to create many medieval and early modern nautical charts

(Figs. 1-3). The prevalence of these lines and shapes appears to vary across the centuries. For example, the serrated line, with maxima spaced widely, is favored over the undulating line for depicting regions with low toponym density until at least the mid-fifteenth century. This is, it is the 'default' line type.¹⁵ By the sixteenth century, lobed capes and crenellated coasts become more commonplace. Some individual authors also have peculiarities. Benincasa's work, for instance, frequently employs stacked circular bays, cordiform biting, and bitten serrated capes.

Since charts are drawings with a codified graphical lexicon, we cannot not treat all their components as uniformly information-laden. That is to say that we should not focus on the precise size and angle of a given serration on a coastline, but treat the serration itself as a unit. Indeed, the experienced cartographer, knowing this chart's visual language, need not concern themselves with copying *every tiny*

Some fundamental cape shapes		
Lobed cape	Swollen lobed cape	Trefoil lobed cape
Triangular serrated cape	Quadrilateral serrated cape	Clubbed quadrilateral serrated cape

Figure 2: Some fundamental cape shapes on manuscript nautical charts

Some fundamental bay shapes	
	Circular bay
	Cordiform bay
	Stacked circular (snowman) bay

Figure 3: Some fundamental bay shapes on manuscript nautical charts

Figure 4: Detail of map included in a 16th-century copy of Cristoforo Buondelmonti's *Liber Insularum Arcipelagi*. 22 x 19 cm. Ink and gouache on paper. Bibliothèque Nationale de France Latin 4823, fol.1v.

Figure 5: Detail of an unsigned ca. 16th-century chart with pen tests in the form of two fundamental line types of nautical cartography. 28 x 39 cm. Ink on parchment. Bibliothèque Nationale de France, CPL GE D-7884.

detail on the coastlines, but should be able to copy what is needed to anchor the general courses of shores, and then execute and supplement those lines with the needed shapes signifying different coastal features.

Such an approach is seen in the preliminary drawing of the representation of the Aegean Sea in a sixteenth-century copy of Cristoforo Buondelmonti's *Liber Insularum Arcipelagi* (Fig. 4). The draftsman saw through the specificity of their cartographic model and rendered at first only the sweep of coastline without elaboration. That cartographers were able to conceive of coastlines as rhythmic patterns of repeating shapes is also evident in an anonymous cartographer's pen test on the side of an unusual and seemingly unfinished chart of the sixteenth century stored in the Bibliothèque Nationale de France, which takes the shape of a mixed bitten/serrated line (Fig. 5).¹⁶ We may often spot the layperson's approximative grasp of the basic shapes of charts in mappamundi that incorporate portolan-type Mediterranean coasts. This is particularly evident when the producer of a mappamundi tries to extend the nautical chart line style to poorly-known geographical regions, occasionally resulting in a faux specificity that caricatures the language true nautical charts (Fig. 6).

Using a few basic types of lines, convexities (capes), and concavities (bays), combinations can be created almost endlessly (Fig.

Figure 6: A fundamental line type (serrated) applied to regions outside the Mediterranean Sea on the mappamundi in the ca. 1320 copy of the *Liber Secretorum Fidelium Crucis* of Marino Sanudo. Ink and color on parchment. Biblioteca Apostolica Vatican, Cod. Pal. Lat.1362A, fols.1v-2r.

Figure 7: Examples of the generation of hybridized shapes on manuscript nautical charts

Figure 8: Demonstration of implied circles and ovals on the coasts of manuscript nautical charts

7). We can, for instance, add bites to the sides of a quadrilateral serrated cape to create a bitten quadrilateral serrated cape. We

can start with a crenellated line segment, add lobes to the tops of the crenels, and make a lobed crenellated line. We can likewise add the sort of scooped chevron forming the apex of the triangular serrated cape to the top of a row of crenels. Particularly prior to the sixteenth century, there is a persistent, seemingly aesthetically-driven reference to the circle and oval in the elaboration of coastlines on portolan charts (Fig. 8). It is likely that the implied circle found in the bitten line or circular bay were not merely convenient shorthand, but rather, constituted a stylistic preference. Plays on the circle are a recurrent device in Gothic curvilinear tracery, especially in rose windows (including that of the cathedral of Genoa, with whose façade Pietro Vesconte would have been well-acquainted). The characteristic southern European corbel table is likewise reminiscent of the bitten line given in Fig. 1.¹⁷ The availability of such architectural motifs in the imagination of mapmakers is clear in the churches and castles embellishing Albini de Canepa's 1489 chart in the James Ford Bell Library (call number 1489 mCa), which feature crenellated walls, and several types of corbel tables resembling serrated and bitten nautical chart lines. These are just a few examples several of the shapes seen on the portolan charts might have been more common in the medieval/early modern visual environment than in ours; when coming up with ways to code hydrographic features, such shapes would not only have been memorable and legible, but pleasing and familiar.¹⁸ Such a preoccupation with the geometrical forms created or insinuated by coastlines is less salient in some earlier charts, like the Carte

Pisane and Lucca Chart, and all but absent works of Battista Agnese (where miniature paintings and luxe materials do the heavy lifting).

In the sections to follow, I will start by drawing on archaeological and textual evidence to identify and explain the copying processes practiced in the two-dimensional arts between 1300 and the mid-seventeenth century. Unfortunately, manual tasks like copying are often poorly-suited to verbal description. Although words are inferior to demonstration, understanding these processes is a prerequisite to identifying their use. After detailing the way a copying method works, I will pull from the every-growing corpus of high-resolution photographs of manuscript nautical charts to highlight cases of these techniques in action.¹⁹ Although in situ confirmation is warranted in some instances, we are in an unprecedented moment of digital access to the widely-dispersed corpus of charts; seizing on resources such as the Medea-Chart Database (<http://www.medea.fc.ul.pt>) to remotely pore through the archives, one may confront ample evidence for how chartmakers actually copied. These artisanal practices are not lost to time, but have merely awaited our patient attention.

Copying by eye: The use of the squaring grid

Although this paper will primarily address bridged copying methods, a few words ought to be said about squaring grids, an aid to copying by eye. Until the pantograph, the squaring grid may have been chartmakers' best hope for reproducing a model chart at a new size without introducing proportional distortions. Squaring grids are referenced in numerous artists' handbooks, and an illustration and description of their application to cartography is given by Martín Cortés de Albacar in his *Breve compendio de la sphaera y de arte de navegar* (Fig. 9).²⁰ Copying with a grid need not leave marks on the model, since a frame with strings could be used in lieu of inscribed lines. Any trace of grid lines is likelier to be found

Figure 9: A woodblock print of a squaring grid from the *Breve Compendio* of Martin Cortes of 1551, fol. 67r.

Figure 10: Detail of an anonymous 17th-century chart of Newfoundland and the Gulf of Saint Laurence, showing a drawing mistake (indicated by white arrows) arising from the use of a squaring grid to copy a model by eye. Ink and pencil on paper. National Archives of the Netherlands, 4.VEL, 516.

Figure 11: 1649 chart of the Indian Ocean by João Teixeira Albernaz with a sketchy grid, seemingly executed in graphite. 65 x 50 cm. Ink on paper. Bibliothèque Nationale de France, GE SH 18 PF 213 DIV 3 P 2/1 D.

on a copy made by this method, since such a frame would hinder drawing. It is at first glance it is therefore surprising that so few charts bear any hint of a grid. Although Corradino Astengo has noted two unfinished charts of the seventeenth century with grids possibly placed to aid the drawing of coastlines, these are a small fraction of the hundreds of charts surviving from the period under discussion.²¹ This fact needs not imply that grids were not used, but may instead suggest that their primary application was in the creation of new workshop models for bridged copying. Such artisanal kit is often lost, discarded, or destroyed over the years. Nonetheless, surviving exemplars can provide some instructive insights relevant to the subsequent discussion of bridged copying.

The unfinished seventeenth-century chart of Newfoundland held at the National Archive of the Netherlands (4.VEL, no. 516) includes both a squaring grid in ink, a preliminary drawing in graphite, and ink lines. The fact that the grid lines are indelible should force us to question whether this is a copy made using a squaring grid, a model for copying by squaring grid, or a chart created by some other means, with grid lines added afterwards. In the case of this chart, an error committed by the chartmaker gives us the answer. If we look at the preliminary drawing, we see that the cartographer miscounted the squares in their grid, and began to place their preparatory sketch in the wrong cell. Later, realizing this mistake, they redraw and inked the stretch of coast at its proper position in the neighboring square (Fig. 10). The preparatory sketch on the chart exemplifies the roughness and hesitancy of copies made by eye; we should keep this in mind when observing the comparatively confident preliminary markmaking permitted by bridged copying methods.

The anonymous chart discussed above represents a case of a new chart produced with the aid of a grid. For a gridded chart perhaps serving as a *model* for copying, one can look to an uncolored ink chart of João Teixeira Albernaz dating to 1649 housed at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France. The squaring grid on this chart appears to have been hastily-drawn in graphite to facilitate copying of Albernaz's coastlines; when and by whom it was drawn is unclear (Fig. 11).

Bridged copying methods in depth

As I have already stated, copying involves the lifting of graphical information from a model and its deposition on a final support. This can be a purely visual process, as in the case of the squaring grid, or it can be controlled by bridging procedures.²² A first bridging procedure is backlit tracing. This is a method by which a light source placed behind the model and final support renders both sheets translucent, simultaneously 'lifting' and (ephemerally) 'depositing' graphical, with the copyist mainly responsible for fixing and finalizing the desired lines.²³ Alternatively, a translucent intermediary sheet, functionally identical to tracing paper, could be used to lift graphical information from a model. Translucent intermediaries attested in artists' and cartographers' treatises include: isinglass (i.e. fish glue), a pane of glass, and linseed-oil treated parchment or paper.²⁴ Because neither a film of dried fish glue nor a pane of glass will allow the tracing of the model to be looped in with a method that transfers the design onto a final support, we can eliminate them as options.

Let us now turn to the methods that allow the copyist to deposit lines taken from the model onto a final support. I will use three terms to refer to the lines on a chart that anticipate the final drawing. Preliminary drawing will mean any drawing created to aid the positioning of ink lines. When the preliminary drawing arises from copying by eye or by imagination, it will be termed a preparatory sketch. When, on the other hand, the preliminary drawing is mediated by a bridging procedure, we shall call it a transfer drawing.

Stencils

Stencils are the most ancient of bridged copying methods that I shall address. From ruler to stencil is a very short trip of the imagination, a trip made by artisans working in diverse media and from diverse cultures; that stencil use continues to the present day is a testament to their conceptual straightforwardness and reliability. They have been used in European mural painting from at least the medieval period, particularly for repeated ornaments.²⁵ Catherine Hess points to their role in the workshops of sixteenth-century Italian ceramicists executing narrative paintings copied from prints or drawings.²⁶ Stencils were also implicated in the coloring of Syro-Egyptian ceramics from the Muslim necropolis Kom el-Dikka, in an archaeological layer

including Fayyumi and Fustat Fatimid wares as well as Italo-Sicilian proto-majolica.²⁷ Stencil use has usually been inferred by features of a finished work; only very rarely have the stencils themselves survived.²⁸ It is from the features of finished charts that we may deduce stencil use.

The preparation of a stencil for chart copying might work as follows: using a translucent intermediary sheet, the model chart is traced. The tracing is cut neatly along the newly-drawn lines to make one or several stencils. If the translucent intermediary sheet lacks the rigidity necessary, a hardier stencil could be made by pasting several sheets together, one on top of the other, to create a thicker, more rigid sheet prior to cutting.²⁹ The stencil is then traced onto the final support in a dry medium, since liquid media can flow under a stencil and mar the line.³⁰ Two media well-suited for stencil tracing are drypoint and metalpoint. Drypoint is markmaking by pressure, familiar to all who have tried to write on a pad of paper with a pen that has run out of ink. This 'medium' was commonly used by cartographers to position the hidden circle when planning a chart's rhumb network. Indeed, drypoint is the natural extension of another ancient and enduring writing method: inscribing on a wax tablet with a stylus. Although indelible, drypoint can be extremely discreet. It was regularly used for the ruling of manuscript pages in the early medieval period, but also found applications in recording glosses, making compilation notes, and working out drawings. Metalpoint is a catch-all term for the still poorly-understood collection of metallic writing implements employed the medieval period and revived in the Renaissance. Both hold a very fine point, which is beneficial to tracing around a stencil.

Two facets of the graphical character of a nautical chart complicate the creation of stencils, but may be the key to spotting instances of their use. The first relates to the islands on charts. A stencil is ideal for capturing unbroken lines and closed figures, but the nautical chart includes a combination of long, rather continuous lines (mainland coasts) and closed lines unconnected to the mainland (island coasts). A solution would be to create a stencil for the water itself, with the islands' positions fixed by cutting holes into the 'water stencils.' To save labor and improve the durability of such a stencil, it is likely that only the major islands would be cut out, with the smaller ones inked in subsequently by eye. If, on the other hand, a stencil for land were produced, the cartographer might adapt their approach by fabricating separate stencils for larger islands and positioning by eye or with the aid of a measuring device like a proportional compass. The degree to which island location varies across works by a chartmaker may therefore indicate whether one or the other sort of stencil figured into a chart's creation.³¹

The second obstacle to copying charts with stencils is the intricacy of the coastlines on so many charts, most particularly in the Mediterranean Sea, where the earliest charts were produced. It would be tricky to cut stencils simultaneously tough enough to be reused repeatedly, and yet inclusive of all these

minor graphical features. A chartmaker might therefore fashion stencils with some degree of simplification.³² With the transfer drawing completed and the main trajectories of coasts locked in, fussier elaborations could be added back in during the final ink drawing.

This lengthy preamble prepares us to imagine how we might recognize a chart copied with stencils; I will focus on those related to draftsmanship. If a stencil were exploited, we should first expect to find a subtle preliminary drawing, in a dry medium. To establish that this drawing relates to a stencil, we must distinguish it from a freehand preparatory sketch. A stencil-aided transfer drawing will likely lack some of the details seen on the final ink drawing, may show rounding out or two-stroke construction of sharp vertices, and will have less ‘uncertainty’ (Fig. 12). One last tip-off for of stencil use could appear in the final ink lines

Figure 12: Potential graphical signatures of tracing around stencils (stencil is represented by the area in medium gray, final support in light gray, transfer drawing in dark gray)

themselves. If the writing implement accidentally slipped underneath a stretch of stencil because it wasn't flush to the final support, the draftsman might then have to correct themselves by flattening out the stencil and redrawing. If the final inking were executed by an individual other than the one who did the stencil transfer drawing, or by the same person but under some distraction, this kind of slip might be mindlessly reproduced in the final ink drawing.³³ The ‘doublings’ of a preparatory sketch would not be inked in this way, because a sketch's inherently approximative character discourages strict replication to any and every drafted line. More generally, across works by one author, the use of a stencil or other fixed-scale transfer process should lead to a body of work marked by groupings of charts with very similar drawings executed at identical or nearly identical sizes.³⁴

Summing up, to demonstrate that a stencil was used, we must look at the degree of conformity achieved in the ink coastlines across charts with coastlines of the same size by a single author (to rule out copying by eye), attempt to detect preliminary drawings, and figure out whether the features of those preliminary drawings match those expected of stencil-constrained transfer drawings.

As will be demonstrated below, the works of Pietro Vesconte, Perrino Vesconte, Albertino de Virga, the anonymous author of the Lyon Cornaro atlas, Giacomo Girolodi, and Grazioso Benincasa may all have employed stencils to create transfer drawings in drypoint (or for the Vescontes, metalpoint). In the case of the Pietro Vesconte and Grazioso Benincasa, we shall see that the character of the final ink drawings precludes copying by eye, with or without a grid. There is no sign of any of the other copying methods handled in the sections to come on these charts (although for the Vescontes and Benincasa, limited visibility

Figure 13: Line drawings of shared coastlines in Pietro Vesconte's 1320 atlas at the Bibliothèque Municipale de Lyon, MS 175. Black: chart of the eastern Mediterranean and Aegean Sea (fol. 4r). Gray: chart of Sicily to Crete (fol. 4v). Light gray: chart of the Adriatic Sea (fol. 8v).

Figure 14: Line drawings of shared coastlines in Pietro Vesconte's 1320 atlas at the Bibliothèque Municipale de Lyon, MS 175. Black: chart of the eastern Mediterranean and Aegean Sea (fol. 4r). Light gray: chart of the Black Sea and Marmora Sea (fol. 3r).

of the preliminary drawings makes it impossible to discard the option of backlit tracing). Rather than treat a specific author, for the moment I will move through this evidence related to stencil use according to type, first demonstrating the unlikelihood of freehand drawing where multiple surviving works permit comparison, and then giving images showing the existence of preliminary stencil-compatible transfer drawings and highlighting some of their features.

Let us begin by dispensing with copying by eye by examining selected works of Pietro Vesconte and Grazioso Benincasa; because of the volume and character of outputs surviving from these authors, we have the chance to identify and directly compare multiple charts copied from the same model. The 1320 atlas of Pietro Vesconte housed at the Bibliothèque Municipale de Lyon (MS 175) includes seven charts. Each of these charts has stretches of coastlines that are repeated on another chart in the atlas. This allows us to assess how one author, in a restricted window of time, depicted the same geographical regions on multiple occasions. Figures 13 and 14 use digital line drawings to compare these repeated stretches of coastlines on different charts in the atlas, holding real-world ratio of drawing sizes

constant.³⁵ While not identical, any discontinuities between them might be attributed to the extent of simplification on a stencil or minor liberties during the inking process. That repeated coastlines across the atlas are close to identical, and that the individual charts of the atlas can be combined into a single chart of larger coverage, further suggests that the model used by Vesconte for this work was a single, whole-Mediterranean chart measuring around 50 cm x 90 cm (Plate 1).

The uniformity accomplished by Grazioso Benincasa's drawings is even more striking.³⁶ Plate 2 gives a comparison of the coastlines on the chart including the Black Sea, Aegean Sea, and Eastern Mediterranean from three Benincasa atlases kept at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France. Again holding real-world size ratio constant, a line drawing of the coastlines from Benincasa's 1467 atlas (hereafter BnF 6269) was overlaid onto photographic reproductions of the corresponding chart from the 1466 atlas (hereafter BnF

Plate 1: Digital line drawings of the coastlines from Pietro Vesconte's 1320 atlas (Bibliothèque municipale de Lyon, MS 175) overlaid to form a contiguous chart with larger coverage. Separate colors are used to distinguish between coastlines from each of the atlas's seven charts. Gray boxes represent the edges of each bifolium. Scale bar is divided into increments of ten centimeters. The approximate dimensions of the model chart needed to produce the atlas, assuming the use of a fixed-scale copying method, are given in centimeters on the bottom right.

Plate 2: The coastlines, in blue, of the chart including parts of the eastern Mediterranean, Aegean Sea, and Black Sea in Benincasa's atlas of 1467 (Bibliothèque Nationale de France, CPL GE DD-6269) overlaid on the corresponding chart in the atlas of 1466 (CPL GE DD-2779) (left) and a second atlas of 1467 (CPL GE DD-1988) (right). The relative sizes of each digital reproduction and the overlaid blue coastlines have been held constant.

Plate 3: Digital line drawings of the coastlines from five charts in Grazioso Benincasa's 1467 atlas (Bibliothèque Nationale de France, CLP GE DD-6269) overlaid to form a contiguous chart with larger coverage. Separate colors are used to distinguish between coastlines from each of the charts. Gray boxes represent the edges of each bifolium. No gray box is given for the easternmost bifolium because it contains two separate regional segments that require repositioning to line up with corresponding coasts on the "neighboring" chart. Scale bar is divided into increments of ten centimeters. The approximate dimensions of the model chart needed to produce the atlas, assuming the use of a fixed-scale copying method, are given in centimeters on the bottom right.

2779) and a second atlas of 1467 (hereafter BnF 1988). In all three atlases, this particular chart is noncontiguous, containing depictions of two separate regions: the eastern Mediterranean Sea/southern Aegean Sea, and Black Sea/Marmora Sea/northern Aegean Sea. Therefore, to facilitate comparison, the blue drawing of the coastlines from BnF 6269 was split into these two sections and translated vertically or horizontally to align with the coasts on the charts from BnF 2779 and 1988.³⁷ The conformity across the three drawings is astounding. The courses of rivers, however, do not follow the same trajectory across these works, which makes perfect sense if the charts were drawn with stencils. As I have already mentioned, stencils exert a pressure towards simplification and the removal of nonessential information, since added details bring about reduced stencil durability. It bears repeating that despite varying page dimensions across the three atlases, the drawings are of identical size; we must not be too hasty in grouping

Figure 15: Drypoint marks on the chart of the Aegean Sea, eastern Mediterranean Sea, and Black Sea in the anonymous 14th-century Cornaro atlas of Lyon. 31 x 23 cm. Ink, gold, and color on parchment pasted to wooden boards. Bibliothèque Municipale de Lyon, MS 179, fol.3.

Figure 16: Drypoint marks on the 1422 Giacomo Girolodi chart of the Mediterranean Sea, Black Sea, and western Europe. 88 x 51 cm. Ink and color on parchment. Bibliothèque Nationale de France, GE C-5088 (RES).

Figure 17: Drypoint or metalpoint marks on the ca. 1321 Perrino Vesconte chart of Italy. 29 x 29 cm. Ink, gold, and color on parchment pasted onto wooden boards. Zentralbibliothek Zürich, R.P.4, karte 4

Figure 18: Drypoint marks on the 1409 Albertino de Virga chart of the Mediterranean Sea, Black Sea, and western Europe. 68 x 43 cm. Ink and color on parchment. Bibliothèque Nationale de France, CPL GE D-7900 (RES).

charts according to the measurements of their support. In addition, the separate charts of BnF 6269 (and probably, at the very least, BnF 1988 and 2779) can be combined with almost no discrepancies into a chart of greater coverage, hinting at the use of a single, larger chart as the ultimate model for Benincasa's atlas pages (Plate 3).

We can now turn to another mark of production compatible with stencil use: subtle, self-assured transfer drawings in what appear to be metalpoint or drypoint.³⁸ Figures 15-18 give examples of the appearance of some such drawings. Note in particular the Lyon Cornaro atlas, Perrino Vesconte atlas, and de Virga chart,³⁹ in whose preliminary drawings we observe exactly the sort of graphical abridgements expected from a stencil-aided transfer. These glimpses of preliminary drawings are in all

likelihood the tip of the iceberg; in the case of drypoint, such marks are invisible in all but the highest resolution photographic reproductions and even then can be seen only with felicitous angles of incident light.⁴⁰

This section has argued that stencils were used in the early days of chart copying on the grounds of historical plausibility, the character of preliminary drawings, and process of elimination. In situ examination of the charts will be necessary to verify this hypothesis and provide additional examples, particularly for charts with drypoint preliminary drawings. Distinguishing a stencil-aided transfer from a backlit tracing demands extremely close study of these first drawings; exploring the possibility of this copying method will hopefully serve as a provocation for such research in archives. Even at this early phase of study, however, some trends have emerged. All the charts potentially made with stencils, or possessing an extremely fine preliminary drawing whose origins may relate to either stencil or backlit tracing, date to a particular time frame (ca. 1300 to ca. 1475), are the work of Italian-born cartographers, and include only sparing painted adornment to the coastlines.

Pricking and pouncing

Pricking and pouncing is an ingenious method of reproducing graphical features that is commonly agreed to have originated in China and landed in Italy as a byproduct of intensifying Sino-European trade in the early fourteenth century.⁴¹ To exploit this method, the copyist uses a needle (or any sharp-tipped instrument) to prick a series of holes along the lines of the model. The perforated model is placed on top of the final support, and a small bag holding powder of an appropriate color is patted along the pierced lines. This powder passes through the loose weave of the pounce bag, through the holes on the model, and onto the final support, leaving a ghostly 'connect-the-dots' that can be traced over in ink. Because different materials can be used for pounce powder, it is a technique adaptable to both local resources and the color of the final support.⁴² It can be executed without dirtying a finished graphic work by placing the model on top of an additional sheet (called in other contexts a substitute cartoon) and pricking both at once. It can be rendered wholly non-invasive on the finished model by first tracing the model's design onto a translucent intermediary sheet (thus transforming the translucent sheet into the model), and then pricking the tracing. Given the adaptability of this copying method, it is not surprising that it found uses across a variety of crafts; it is referenced in handbooks on panel painting, embroidery, and miniature painting dating from the fourteenth to eighteenth centuries,⁴³ and attested by extant pricked patterns and pounce-dotted artefacts.⁴⁴ The promiscuity of the pouncing method should obviously not be taken to imply a smooth adoption and uniform application across crafts or workshops. My point, rather, is to indicate again that in the case of the copying methods addressed in this text, the boundaries between traditional types of graphic arts were permeable, just as professional identities of artisans could be more mutable. Notwithstanding the tremendous differences between a nautical chart and a piece of embroidery, the manufacture of either

often involved the transfer of a two-dimensional design from one surface to another, and the insularity of contemporary scholarship was not reflected by the demonstrable overlap of relevant practices in pre-modern crafts.

With the first mentions of pricking and pouncing dating to the late 1300s, it was only at the turn of the seventeenth century that the technique was noted in print with regard to the geographic depictions, in the *Nautica Mediterranea* of Bartolomeo Crescentio.⁴⁵ Crescentio's allusion to pouncing follows a lengthy exposition on the construction of a map 'Geograficamente,' i.e. by plotting locations according to longitude and latitude. It was with evident dismay that Crescentio concedes that in his day most charts are made by 'huomini idioti' who concern themselves with mindlessly replicating, rather than thoughtfully constructing, cartographic images. Crescentio gives no guidance on *what* to prick on the model, but is oddly specific on the material to be used for pounce dust: well-ground indigo, for only this powder is 'suitable to create [the needed] effect' (*sola questa polvere è atta à fare questo effetto*). While indigo, a natural dye, does have a certain staining power when used as a paint, it is unclear whether Crescentio insists on it because of any special virtues of the powder itself, or is merely anticipating subsequent tinting of the waters in blue and wishes to promote a material that would blend in well. That other powders were perfectly adequate for pouncing on parchment is clear from Catherine Perrot's guide to miniature painting published in 1686, which recommends pouncing onto parchment in charcoal, then tracing over the pounce dots in metalpoint, and finally erasing the remaining dust with a bit of bread.⁴⁶

Pricking and pouncing presents both obvious advantages relative to stencils, and drawbacks. On the one hand, a pricked model could easily capture the lines on a chart unconnected to the mainland (islands). On the other hand, level of detail in the lines of many nautical charts would require a density of pricking matching or exceeding that seen in the upper-extremes in other applications of the technique, and still produce ambiguities that could only be resolved by careful visual reference to a finished chart. I have found, using a representative segment a chart of Perrino Vesconte, that close conformity between model and copy would presuppose around nineteen pounce dots per centimeter of line; hardly a sustainable approach to chart reproduction.⁴⁷ To overcome this problem, a copyist might home in on capes as a way to simplify the process, and prick only headlands. Only the capes on serrated coasts, however, readily lend themselves to such a shortcut. Whatever the hypothetical plan of attack, we must realize that in choosing where on the model to prick, a copyist is tacitly choosing which positions on the chart contain essential information. It is an active selection and prioritization influenced by the graphical features of the model and necessitated by the constraints of this copying technique; here, as in nearly all of the methods this text addresses, the shape of the Mediterranean has entered the draftsman's purview.

Figure 19: Pounce dots on the ca. 1475 printed copy of Dati's *Sfera* published by Gabriele di Pietro in Venice, with hand-drawn marginal illustrations of coastlines. Folios measure 29 x 29 cm. Ink on paper. Library of Congress, PQ4621.D17 S4 1475, image file no. 40.

Figure 20: Pounce dots on the depiction of Crete in a 16th-century copy of the *Liber Insularum Arcipelagi* of Cristoforo Buondelmonti. 29 x 20.5 cm. Ink and color on paper. Bibliothèque Nationale de France, GE FF-9351 (RES).

dots on extant charts. Although the pessimist might conclude that either perfect erasure or tracing over of pounce dots dooms further inquiry, it will be shown in the next section, however, that cartographers were not uniformly fastidious in effacing residuum of the copying process. Indeed, signs of pounce dots for placing coastlines do

survive in some geographical depictions connected to the nautical chart tradition.⁴⁸

Our first two examples of pounced coastlines are found in isolarii of the fifteenth century: in a copy of Dati's *Sfera* produced in Venice around the year 1475 and attributed to Gabriele di Pietro, now kept at the Library of Congress, and in a copy of Cristoforo Buondelmonti's *Liber Insularum Arcipelagi* made between 1465 and 1475 and currently held by the Bibliothèque Nationale de France (Figs. 19 and 20). Especially in the Buondelmonti codex, we can observe that tracing over pounce dots in ink does not irretrievably obscure them; by impregnating the ink with (here, presumably carbon) powder, the color of

Figure 21: Anonymous 17th-century chart of the Balearic Islands and eastern coast of Spain. 48 x 35 cm. Ink and color on paper. Biblioteca Nacional do Brasil, CAM.05,006.

ink is altered where it lays on top of pounce dots. As the ink fades, the location of pounce dots becomes increasingly apparent. Note as well the way pouncing is utilized in the two codices; where in the *Liber Insularum* the pounce dots are closely-spaced and there is a tight correspondence between final ink line and pounce dots, the draftsman responsible for the *Sfera* drawings uses only sparse dots as a rough guide. Such diversity highlights artisans' idiosyncratic working methods,

The most direct demonstrations that pricking and pouncing played a role in the reproduction of nautical charts would be the recovery of pricked models, pricked substitute cartoons, or the detection of pounce

varying perspectives on their source material, and agency in the process of copying.

A final example of pouncing used in chartmaking comes from an anonymous French seventeenth-century atlas housed at the Biblioteca Nacional do Brasil. In regions of the chart where the coastlines are adorned with translucent pink paint, particularly on the chart depicting the east of Spain and Balearics, signs of pounce dots are unmistakable (Fig. 21). In some stretches of coast where the paint has flaked off, faint bluish-tinged remnants of pounce can also be observed; although photographs alone cannot prove the material used for this pounce, its color and apparent staining properties are compatible with the indigo *Crescentio* endorsed.

Considering the technical hurdles to pricking and pouncing tortuous coastlines, it may not be a coincidence that two out of the three cases of this method I could find were in *isolarii*, which depict coastlines at a larger scale and thus tend to have fewer curves and vertices per centimeter of line. Alternatively, the survival of pounce dots on these cartographic works could be attributed to their paper support; the ‘tooth’ of paper might have trapped pounce dots better than parchment, making them harder to erase. Pending further evidence, however, there is little concrete proof that pricking and pouncing played a major role in European chart reproduction in the period between 1300 and 1600.

Carbon transfer

Emerging on the copying scene by the fifteenth century, carbon transfer presents an easy way to achieve comprehensive, coherent transmission of the graphical information on a model. The copyist needs only an exemplar, a final support, a stylus, and (if they do not wish to dirty the reverse of the exemplar) a sheet of either smoked or charcoal- or chalk-rubbed paper. Making a sandwich with model on top, then carbon-treated sheet (dirty-side down), and then final support, the copyist passes a stylus along the lines on the model. This pressure pushes carbon powder onto the final support, and, if the copyist has been careful, the disposition of the transferred powder mirrors the lines of the model. These marks then direct the finishing of the graphic object in a permanent medium (in our case, the coasts, in ink). The benefit of carbon transfer over stencils is its ability to capture connected and unconnected lines with equal ease (helping resolve the dilemma of positioning islands and minor hydrographic features). It may likewise be preferable to pricking and pouncing in terms of labor expenditure, and because it produces a transfer drawing with less visual ambiguity. The downside of carbon transfer is that it entails a substantial deposition of transfer medium on the final support, plausibly making it harder to erase or hide such marks of copying.

Infrared reflectography has demonstrated the use of the carbon transfer process among Italian panel painters since at least the fifteenth century, and several artists’ treatises dating to the sixteenth

Figure 22: 'Blocking in' sailing hazards in the carbon transfer drawing on a chart of Newfoundland south to the Caribbean by Hercules O'Doria. 31.3 x 41.1 cm. Ink, gold, and color on parchment. John Carter Brown Library, Codex Z 5 / 2-SIZE.

Figure 23: Chart of northwest Africa in a 1583 copy of *Les premieres Oeuvres de Jacques de Vaulx Pilote pour le Roy*. Folios measure 44 x 59 cm. Ink and color on parchment. Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Français 150, fol. 7v.

Figure 24: Detail of a chart of the Indian Ocean in an atlas attributed to Battista Agnese. Folios measure 22.2 x 31.7 cm. Ink and color on parchment. Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Latin 18249, fol. 7r.

century bring up the technique.⁴⁹ Just a year after Giorgio Vasari's reference to the method in his 1550 *Vite de' più eccellenti pittori, scultori e architettori*, carbon transfer is cited as a way of copying charts' coastlines in the *Breve compendio de la sphaera y de arte de navegar* of Martín Cortés de Albarca.⁵⁰ The efficacy of the method for copying the coasts of nautical charts was corroborated experimentally by Kevin Sheehan.⁵¹

The primary indication that a chart's coastlines were laid down using this method is, unsurprisingly, traces of the carbon transfer drawing itself in the environs of the ink coastlines. A positive identification of a carbon transfer drawing should include, first of all, confirmation that the observed preliminary drawing is in a carbon-based material (but probably not graphite, which would have been comparatively costly).⁵² Next, we must rule out direct drawing (for instance, with a stick of vine charcoal). Experiments with period-appropriate materials may refine this discrimination process.⁵³ We can also use context clues to differentiate between transfer drawings and preparatory sketches. When only the coastlines of a heavily-decorated chart show the smudgy, grayish-black lines I posit come from carbon transfer, it is hard to argue that we are in the presence of a preparatory sketch. If we were, why would we not find similar marks close by the other elements on the chart?

Some of the most arresting examples of what appear to be carbon transfer drawings are encountered in the works of Hercules O'Doria (1592 atlas, John Carter Brown Library, Codex Z 5/2-SIZE), Jacques de Vaulx (sixteenth-century copies of *Les premieres Oeuvres de Jacques de Vaulx Pilote...*, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Français 9175 and 150), and Battista Agnese (ca. 1553 attributed atlas,

Figure 25: The rounding out of an estuary in the final ink drawing on a 1592 chart of Newfoundland south to the Caribbean by Hercules O’Doria. 31.3 x 41.1 cm. Ink, gold, and color on parchment. John Carter Brown Library, Codex Z 5 / 2-SIZE.

Huntington Library, HM 26; attributed atlas, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Latin 18249; attributed atlas, Zentralbibliothek Zürich, ms C 48; signed atlas, John Carter Brown Library, Codex Z 3 / 2-SIZE) (Figs. 22-24).⁵⁴ All three authors share a strategy for copying the stippled shoals on their model charts: during the carbon transfer, they simply ‘block in’ the zone they will later fill with ink dots. Likewise, all three authors tend to treat the transfer with a certain laxity when doing a final ink drawing, and occasionally yield to an aestheticizing impulse (seen, for example, in the widened curves on an inlet near Cauo Lauello on the

O’Doria chart of Newfoundland, Fig. 25). These shortcuts and amendments may reflect an awareness that their specific clients did not demand scrupulous replication of a given model; getting the “gist” of whatever version of the geography the cartographer had at hand was sufficient.

Given the tremendous volume of works attributed to Agnese, we have the chance to see how a cartographer’s selected copying method and attitude towards their model affected finished charts. In charts where it is possible to follow the marks of carbon transfer, Agnese has copied the following items: main coastlines, inlets, islands, the overall shape of blocks of stippled shoals, and many x-shaped sailing hazards (apparently rendering them more as a dot or dash than an x).⁵⁵ I have not observed any symptoms of carbon transfer on the charts’ elements (scalebar, wind roses, etc.) or on the decorative figures in the margins and inland regions of the charts.

If we compare, as we did with Pietro Vesconte, repeating stretches of coast across the pages

Figure 26: Line drawings of coastlines in the ca. 1544 atlas attributed to Battista Agnese and kept at the Huntington Library, HM 26. Black: the chart of the Aegean Sea and eastern Mediterranean (fol.12). Gray: the chart of the Black Sea and Marmora Sea (fol. 12v).

Figure 27: : Line drawings of coastlines in the ca. 1544 atlas attributed to Battista Agnese and kept at the Huntington Library, HM 26. Black: the chart of the western Mediterranean (fol. 10). Gray: the chart of Italy and the central Mediterranean (fol. 10v).

Plate 4: Photo mosaic of four charts in the ca. 1544 atlas attributed to Battista Agnese (Huntington Library, HM 26), with repeated coastlines across charts overlapped. A model including the whole Mediterranean and Black Sea, with coastlines similarly disposed to those seen in this photomosaic, was probably used to create these four atlas charts. The ratio of page sizes was held constant because a fixed-scale copying method is assumed, and borders were trimmed to improve legibility of the collage.

Plate 5: The same atlas as in Plate 4 (Huntington Library, HM 26) represented as digital vector line drawings. Separate colors are used to distinguish between coastlines from each of the charts. Gray boxes represent the area enclosed in the border on each chart page. Scale bar is divided into increments of ten centimeters. The approximate dimensions of the model chart needed to produce the atlas, assuming the use of a fixed-scale copying method, are given in centimeters on the bottom left and bottom right.

of an atlas, we can see how Agnese's casual replication of the carbon-transferred model impacts the level of conformity he achieves across copies (Figs. 26-27). Atlas HM 26, attributed to Agnese and kept at the Huntington Library, contains six regional charts depicting with the Mediterranean and eastern Atlantic that share stretches of coastline. Vestiges of carbon transfer are scattered throughout these pages. Four of these charts, with the relative size of the pages held constant, can be combined into a larger image of the Mediterranean (Plates 4-5) suggesting not just a fixed-scale copying method like carbon transfer, but the use of a chart covering the whole Mediterranean and Black Sea as a model. Zooming in to compare sections of coast that are duplicated across the atlas pages (Figs. 26-27), we are presented with more variation in the final drawing than seen in the earlier examples from Vesconte's and Benincasa's atlases. The variation, however, tends to affect more minor details, like the position of inlets. Arguing that bridged copying necessarily leads to serious geographical distortions requires more proof than this. Indeed, based on the evidence currently available, carbon transfer seems to have been adopted by cartographers only from the sixteenth century onward. Until bridged copying is investigated diachronically in greater depth, we might more reasonably point to imperfect rescaling using squaring grids, or the cognitive shortcuts employed when copying by eye, to explain changes or corruption of the picture of the Mediterranean over centuries of manuscript chart transmission.

On a final note, I would like to point out a seemingly symbiotic relationship between carbon transfer and heavily-painted coloring on coastlines, which prompts a 'chicken-or-the-egg' conundrum. Did a trend towards embellishments on coastlines *enable* cartographers to use carbon transfer, an admittedly messy procedure? Or did thickly-painted coastlines emerge as a natural way to at once obscure remnant transfer drawings and impart on these almost mass-produced charts the veneer of luxury? And how do both of these factors relate to the changing trends in fundamental line, cape, and bay shapes in charts? We have taken the evolution and diversification of nautical chart styles largely at face value; granular inquiries into copying methods might offer unexpected insights in this area.

Pantograph

All of the above bridged copying methods share a serious limitation: they are incapable of generating copies of different sizes than the model. The pantograph should have been the breakthrough cartographers were waiting for, allowing them to once and for all escape the tedium and inexactitude of squaring grids for rescaling. The device is essentially a rigid frame forming a parallelogram with a pointer and a writing tool fixed at a distance from each other along the pantograph's freely-swinging arms (Fig. 28). Adjusting the geometry of the frame allows variations in scale between drawings. The copyist uses the pointer to follow

the lines of the model, as if redrawing them. The arms of the pantograph translate this motion to the writing tool, which deposits marks on the final support. For all its arguable utility in rescaling models, we must recognize that the pantograph does not represent a dramatic labor-saving tool for reproducing drawings at the same size. Like carbon transfer, it entails an extensive transfer drawing, and then redrawing in ink. The quill pens used in the period under study require a skillful monitoring of pressure and frequent reloading and testing, and the pantograph arm cannot provide this.

The pantograph also differs from the above methods in that it has an accepted inventor. On the fascinating story behind this device I will give only

the swiftest of synopses. The pantograph was first referenced in print by the German mathematician Christopher Scheiner,⁵⁶ in a text that seems to fit Mario Biagioli's "usus et fabrica" genre.⁵⁷ Scheiner's account of the invention, whether literary or factual, gives us a timeline to start with: it alleges that by the year 1603, an artist called Georgius had devised a simple device that let one make copies at various scales without looking at the copy while drawing. The more Scheiner pressed him, the more tight-lipped Georgius became. Scheiner took it on himself to crack the puzzle, eventually hitting upon the parallelogram pantograph. Scheiner's device, according to the narrative, was unrecognizable to the artist, who in awe conceded that the Jesuit had made a far greater discovery than he. For a couple decades thereafter, Scheiner periodically taught and demonstrated his pantograph, before eventually publishing the *Pantographice, seu Ars dileandi...*, which consists chiefly in geometrical arguments. If Scheiner's account is veridical, two versions of a pantograph existed by 1631: an inferior, but jealously-guarded drawing aid from an artist-polymath; and the simple, but (and Scheiner is emphatic on this point) hard-to-design contraption from Scheiner.⁵⁸ These factors, if we take the story at face value, do not suggest widespread use of pantographs prior to the early seventeenth century.⁵⁹ Although most of the materials involved in building the pantograph itself would have been available for centuries, the markmaking tool Scheiner suggests (*plumbago scriptoria*, i.e. graphite) was not.⁶⁰ It must be clarified experimentally whether period-appropriate alternatives would secure satisfactory results.

Figure 28: The pantograph, configured for enlargement or reduction of a drawing. At the center is the pointer and model. At the left is the fixed point. At the right is the drawing implement and copy. From Christopher Scheiner, *Pantographice, seu, Ars dileandi [...]* (Rome, Ludovico Grignano, 1631), 29.

The best indication that pantographs were used in chartmaking would be the discovery of two charts with different drawing sizes but identical ink coastlines (assuming the pantograph functioned flawlessly, that all the features of the model chart's coastlines were transferred onto the copy chart, and that the ink lines of the copy chart were placed precisely on top of the transfer drawing lines). Another possible hallmark of pantograph bridged copying might come from traces of the transfer drawing itself, which should be in graphite.⁶¹ If satisfactorily intact and extensive, it might be distinguishable from a graphite preparatory sketch, since the angle of the writing implement and pattern of pressure exerted when using a pantograph is different from that achieved when holding the writing tool in hand.⁶² Although I have not noted charts meeting these evidentiary criteria, the possibility that they exist cannot be discounted.

We may also look to Laurent Monsaingeon's interpretation of the layout of an unusual pair of charts, the 1589 chart of Baldasaro Maggiolo in the Archives Départementales des Hautes-Alpes (O1 fi 1534), and the anonymous, undated chart in the Bayerische Staatsbibliothek of Munich (Cod. Icon. 140 fol. 83). Based in part on the orientation and relations of the coastlines on this chart, and in part on a mark of use, Monsaingeon has contended that the charts functioned as models for copying by means of a pantograph 'carousel.'⁶³ If Monsaingeon is correct, the use of pantographs in chart replication significantly antedates the device's accepted year of invention. Monsaingeon's argument that these charts were workshop models is, however, undermined by the fact that both have decorative painting along their coastlines. The Maggiolo chart, moreover, is adorned with shell gold. If these charts were indeed workshop models, whose coasts were to be repeatedly abraded by the pantograph's pointer, it is queer that they have been given such a costly embellishment.

Final Remarks

That the copying process affects the transmitted picture of maritime space is not controversial. But leaving the matter at that is no longer tenable. In this overview, both the presence of evidence for specific copying methods, and early signs of historical trends have been provided. Closer study of the copying process can furnish scholars with crucial new insights. It can give us, first of all, a better understanding of the way chartmakers themselves understood the corpus of information they were responsible for preserving and passing on. Assessment of the ways in which a preliminary or transfer drawing differs from the final ink drawing allows us to see which aspects of hydrography, for a given chartmaker, were fair game for aesthetic interventions or casual interpretation. These vacillations between transfer drawing and final drawing might ultimately open up doors into understanding division of labor in workshop, since pointed, intentional departures from a transfer drawing speak volumes about the sense of authority in the hand placing ink

coastlines. The agency embodied in such deviations is even more evident on the background of sixteenth-century exhortations to work with the best possible model; this advice implies that the copyist should aim for no more and no less than faithfully replicating their exemplar.⁶⁴ A better grasp of such variations can also help clarify when the differences between charts by one author come from an imprecise copying process, and when they are the consequence of the chartmaker using a completely different model.

Moreover, the manner in which the transfer drawing is set down and adapted may prove characteristic for different cartographers, giving map historians a new 'Morellian ear' on which to assign authorship.⁶⁵ Making correlations between the degree of 'luxuriousness' of a chart and conformity between transfer drawing and final ink drawing may also prove helpful for determining which, if any, standards for the drawing of charts were dependent on the chart's destined function.

Historians of hand-drawn nautical charts have the opportunity to take the lead in areas where they have hitherto remained peripheral: in the history of the graphic arts on parchment. Whereas manuscript miniatures are often studied either as unitary works of inescapable uniqueness (a necessary precondition for solid technical examinations), or compared in terms of iconography and 'after-image' copying, scholars of pre-modern nautical charts possess a priceless corpus of artefacts that can shine a light on the way bridged copying worked outside of the usual domain of frescoes and panel paintings. In this survey, I have relied exclusively on readily-available photographic reproductions of charts, and I have deliberately avoided addressing aspects of chart production whose investigation are wholly contingent on microscopy or advanced imaging techniques. Even under the considerable constraints placed by working at a distance from the charts themselves, the frequency with which signs of copying can be discerned and even assigned to methods is striking. While in this essay I touched on those that suggest a specific manner of copying, there are many more cases where the evidence exists but is ambiguous.

The chart and compass quietly revolutionized navigational practices among Mediterranean mariners. These navigational methods were captured, fossilized, and passed on by means of specific copying techniques. The symbiosis between contemporary navigational methods and chart construction, and the way historical copying methods necessitated treating charts as pictures, set the stage for early modern clashes concerning the reform of nautical cartography to reflect 'scientific' ideals. While many aspects of the history of nautical cartography may never be elucidated, the processes behind chart replication are highly amenable to clarification, and are a promising new field of inquiry.

¹ Ramón J. Pujades i Bataller, *Les cartes portolanes: la representació medieval d'una mar solcada* (Barcelona, Lunwerg Editores, 2007), 436.

² It is largely accepted that the number of charts and atlases produced from the late thirteenth to seventeenth century far exceeds the number extant in collections today, and that charts meant to be used on board ships would be the least likely to survive. A good overview of this topic can be found in: Kevin Eric Sheehan, 'The Functions of Portolan Maps: An evaluation of the utility of manuscript nautical cartography from the thirteenth through sixteenth centuries' (PhD diss., Durham University, 2014), 11, 14-15, and 32.

³ This is to separate copying from creating a new chart, which will not be addressed here. The construction of a new chart was traditionally based on courses and estimated distances noted by mariners, with the location of well-known, frequently-visited landmarks serving as aids in construction. Some primary sources giving guidelines for the construction of a new chart include: Alonso de Chaves, *Quatri Partitu en cosmographia practica y por otro nombre llamado espejo de navegantes* (unpublished manuscript, Real Academia de la Historia de Madrid, ms. 9-14-1 2791); Martín Cortés, *Breve compendio de la sphaera y de arte de navegar* (Seville, Antón Alvarez, 1551); and Francisco da Costa, *Tratado de Hidrografia* (quoted in: Luís de Albuquerque, *Duas obras inéditas do Padre Francisco da Costa* (Agrupamento de Estudos de Cartographia Antiga, Separata Lll., Coimbra, Junta de Investigações do Ultramar, 1970), 111).

Another matter is the distinction between a chart intended for navigational purposes and one made for leisurely viewing or planning voyages on land. Martín Cortés notes in 1511 that charts can come in large format or small format (*de punto grande o mayor*, and *de punto pequeño*) (Cortés, *Breve Compendio*, fol. 65r), with small format charts harder to use at sea due to the compression and graphical 'abbreviation' they demand. The extent to which embellishment is indicative of intended function, however, is a matter of speculation. Several of the charts addressed in this paper are ornate and come from atlases. Even showpiece nautical cartographic works tend to include all the aspects expected of charts used in navigation (scale bars, rhumb networks, maritime hazards). There is little reason at present, as other authors have noted, to expect separate lineages of cartographic models depending on intended audience. In the interest of making a first step towards clarifying the replication processes behind nautical chart transmission, I will be drawing on charts of variable decorative content without making any strict divisions between them.

⁴ For instance, in Corradino Astengo, 'The Renaissance Chart Tradition in the Mediterranean', in *The History of Cartography*, 3(part 1), ed. David Woodward (Chicago, University of Chicago Press, 2007), 174-263; in the discussion of printed maps in David Woodward, 'Techniques of Map Engraving, Printing, and Coloring During the Renaissance', in *The History of Cartography*, 3(part 2), ed. David Woodward (Chicago, University of Chicago Press, 2007), 591-611; Mónica Herrera-Casais, 'The nautical atlases of Alī al-sharafi', *Suhayl. International Journal for the History of the Exact and Natural Sciences in Islamic Civilisation* (2008): 223-63.

⁵ Since all the texts affirm that a copyist can and should fully erase marks of their preliminary drawings, it is perfectly understandable that these rare documentary sources have gotten so much attention. If we believe the textual sources, we should not expect to ever encounter signs of process on extant charts.

⁶ Tony Campbell, 'Portolan Charts from the Late Thirteenth Century to 1500', in *The History of Cartography*, 1(part 3), ed.s J.B. Harley and David Woodward (Chicago, University of Chicago Press, 1987), 371-463; Pujades i Bataller, *Les cartes portolanes* (see note 1), 471-85.

⁷ Piero Falchetta, *Marinai, mercanti, cartografi, pittori: ricerche sulla cartografia nautica a Venezia (sec. XIV-XV)* (Atento Veneto, 1995), 77-83.

⁸ Sheehan, 'The Functions of Portolan Maps' (see note 2), 37-108.

⁹ Laurent Monsaingeon, 'Quelques observations (de beotien) sur la carte muette & énigmatique de Baldasarro da Maïolo Vesconte [Gênes], 1589', unpublished paper presented at the International Workshop on the Origin and Evolution of Portolan Chart, Lisbon, 7-8 June 2018.

¹⁰ Attitudes towards copying show tremendous context-dependent variation. Some exemplary treatments of this issue in diverse spheres of image production may be consulted in Richard E. Spear, 'Renaissance and Baroque Originals and Originality', *Studies in the History of Art* 20 (1989): 97-99; Gary Vilkan, 'Ruminations on edible icons: Originals and copies in the art of Byzantium', *Studies in the History of Art* 20 (1989): 47-59; and Ilya Dines, 'The Copying and Imitation of Images in Medieval Bestiaries', *Journal of the British Archaeological Association* 167(1) (2014): 70-82.

¹¹ Copying by eye is often referred to as freehand copying. Since the hand is, strictly speaking, free in any form of copying, I prefer to speak of copying by eye.

¹² Identifying predictable patterns of errors produced when copying by eye would be a great aid to interpreting the relationships among charts. I have reviewed the modern experimental literature, but have found that the body of data is disappointingly small. It is thus premature to draw any conclusions, even if we are willing to extend modern findings to historical practitioners. Nonetheless, I would like here to introduce a couple of potentially useful concepts and papers. First we should note that most studies find that there is a reluctance when copying to tax the working memory; instead, draftsman prefer to look frequently at their model. With that said, some research suggests that more proficient artists are capable of memorizing and reproducing more graphical information than their inexperienced counterparts; this could arguably result in fewer pen stops among experts when copying by eye (since fewer pauses are required to check the model). Another strategy to limit the load on working memory is chunking, also studied in non-visual recall tasks. This tendency towards grouping visual objects might impact the pattern of island dispersion in charts where smaller Aegean Sea islands were drawn by eye. Another central question for our purposes, and addressed by several researchers, is the manner in which a draftsman mentally segments complicated shapes in order to execute a copy.

A few relevant papers on these and related topics are: Kaleem Siddiqi, Kathryn J. Tresness, and Benjamin B. Kimia, 'Parts of visual form: Psychophysical aspects', *Perception* 25, no. 4 (1996): 399-424; Joeri De Winter and Johan Wagemans, 'Contour-based object identification and segmentation: Stimuli, norms and data, and software tools', *Behavior Research Methods, Instruments, & Computers* 36, no. 4 (2004): 604-624; Florian Perdreau and Patrick Cavanagh, 'Drawing experts have better visual memory while drawing', *Journal of Vision* 15, no. 5 (2015): 1-10; Dale J. Cohen, 'Look little, look often: The influence of gaze frequency on drawing accuracy', *Perception & Psychophysics* 67, no. 6 (2005): 997-1009; and Xiaoyang Mao, Omar Galil, Quintcey Parrish, and Chiradeep Sen, 'Evidence of cognitive chunking in freehand sketching during design ideation', *Design Studies* 67 (2020): 1-26.

¹³ Of course, all three senses of copying have played a role in manuscript chart production. Indeed, a single chart can include 'afterimage' copying (cartographer tints coastlines in the same colors as a chart they had seen prior); copying by eye (cartographer places coastal hazards and some small islands by visual approximation); copying by eye with a grid (the likely method for creating new workshop models with new dimensions); and copying with a bridging procedure (the main subject of this paper).

¹⁴ If the copying of islands was frequently executed by eye, Campbell's idea that these distinctive 'puzzle-piece shapes' served a mnemonic function likewise relates to the copying process. Tony Campbell, 'Explanatory notes and wider implications of the colours and shapes used to denote some of the smaller islands and the major estuaries on portolan charts up to 1500', (2011) <<http://www.maphistory.info/PortolanColourNotes.html>>. See also endnote 12.

¹⁵ Misapplication of these fundamental lines may be one way to distinguish between people whose bread-and-butter is chartmaking, and those primarily engaged in other activities. The mappamundi in figure 6, with its inappropriately dense serrations, appears to pertain to the latter category of practitioners. While authors like Vesconte, Benincasa, and even Agnese seemed to realize that regions with a low density of toponyms must be treated with low-density serration, or even undulation, less specialized artisans use an unvarying default line across the entire depicted geography, no matter how well-known or poorly-known to their community.

¹⁶ Attributed to Salvatore Oliva in: Gonçalo de Reparaz i Ruiz, 'Els mapes catalans de la Bibliothèque nationale de Paris', *Estudis Universitaris Catalans* 13 (1928): 218-34. The attribution is noted with some reservations by Corradino Astengo in 'The Renaissance Chart Tradition in the Mediterranean' (see note 4), 240. It is likewise recorded by Richard Pfloderer in his *Census of Portolan Charts and Atlases* (ID number: O101).

¹⁷ This device is surveyed in: C. Edson Armi, 'The Corbel Table', *Gesta* 39(2) (2000): 89-116. Alan Borg, on a related note, traces the visual interrelation between decorative brickwork and manuscript ornament in his examination of the origins of the chevron. Alan Borg, 'The Development of Chevron Ornament', *Journal of the British Archaeological Association* 30(1) (1967): 122-40.

¹⁸ That certain aspects of visual culture may be embodied in different genres of objects is obvious, but has not been adequately considered for the non-figural content on nautical charts. A case study on this broader phenomenon (regarding the use of floral motifs on both medieval wooden ceilings and parchment manuscripts) can be found in: Nataša Golob, 'Floral borders: Some comparative aspects', in *Re-Inventing Traditions: On the Transmission of Artistic Patterns in Late Medieval Manuscript Illumination*, ed.s Joris Corin Heyder and Christine Seidel (Frankfurt, Peter Lang Edition, 2012): 279-300.

¹⁹ Equipped with high-resolution images, the main peril is misinterpreting damage and stray marks accumulated over the centuries.

²⁰ Cortés, *Breve Compendio* (see note 3), fols. 65r-66r and 67r.

²¹ Astengo, 'The Renaissance Chart Tradition in the Mediterranean' (see note 4), 185-96.

²² I have chosen to focus on bridged copying methods that are either well-evidenced in extant charts and textual primary sources, or whose suitability to chart copying is most apparent. Among those techniques that are omitted, given these selection criteria, are the camera obscura (whose inconvenience is only justified when translating complex three-dimensional compositions onto a two-dimensional plane), and a procedure involving carmine lake powder referenced in the 17th century in: Vicente Carducho, *Diálogos de la pintura. Su defesa, origen, essencia, definicion, modos y diferencias* (Madrid, Fr. Martinez, 1633), 134.

²³ This may be achieved using a wooden frame with strings, or a large pane of glass. The former strategy is referenced in: Bartolomeo Crescentio, *Nautica Mediterranea* (Rome, Bartolomeo Bonfadino, 1607), 189. A digitized copy of this book is available at: <https://archive.org/details/nauticamediterra00cres/mode/2up>. To trace using backlighting on such a frame may necessitate a preliminary drawing in a soft medium like charcoal; indeed, this was the method adopted by Kevin Sheehan in his experiments (Sheehan, 'The Functions of Portolan Maps' (see note 2), 70-71). Crescentio seems to favor graphite pencils, telling the copyist to '[disegnare] con sottilissimo lapis le coste.' In cases, however, where the preliminary drawing on a chart is in drypoint or metalpoint, we should be cautious to infer the string-frame backlit tracing method before testing its viability. If, on the other hand, a pane of glass were to be used, we must consider the size of pane that would be needed for the task, and whether a tracing taken on glass would necessitate a preliminary drawing at all.

²⁴ By Cennino Cennini's time (the late fourteenth century), translucent paper was already widely available in the cartulary shops in major trading hubs of Italy. For good measure, though, he provides the fool-proof recipe for the provincial or DIY-inclined artisan. Cennino Cennini, *The Book of the Art of Cennino Cennini. Translated from the Italian, with Notes on Mediæval Art Methods, by Christina J. Herringham*. London: George Allen (1899/c. 1390), 20.

The famed Fabriano paper mill was established sometime in the thirteenth century, but paper was traded and used in the Mediterranean for several centuries prior to this date; by as early as the twelfth century it had accrued a bad reputation among some European scribes. In any case, the widespread circulation of paper in the region considerably antedates the first extant European nautical charts. A good overview of the history of paper in the Mediterranean world can be found in: Abdul Ahad Hannawi, 'The Role of the Arabs in the Introduction of Paper into Europe', *Mela Notes* 85 (2012): 14-29; Raymond Clemens and Timothy Graham, *Introduction to manuscript studies* (Ithaca, Cornell University Press, 2007), 6-9; and Carmen C. Bambach, *Drawing and painting in the Italian Renaissance workshop: theory and practice, 1300-1600* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1999), 34-38.

²⁵ For example, in the fourteenth-century paintings of St. John's church in Mechelin and the Château de Germolles. Anna Bergmans and Marjan Buyle, 'Mural Paintings before Jan van Eyck: a remarkable discovery from around 1400 in St John's Church in Mechelen', *The XVIII Symposium for the Study of Underdrawing and Technology in Painting* (2017); and Christian Degriygn et al., 'Technical study of Germolles' wall paintings: the input of imaging technique', *Virtual Archaeology Review* 7.15 (2016): 1-8.

To move even further back in time, Tomassetti asserts that modular stencils were also used in the Etruscan figural paintings dating to the fourth century BC located in the Tomba degli Scudi in Tarquini. Maria Cristina Tomassetti and Chiara Arrighi, 'Early Evidence of Modular Templates Used to Draw Human Figures on Mural Paintings: The Etruscan Tomba degli Scudi in Tarquinia', *Studies in Conservation* 64.8 (2019): 490-6.

²⁶ Catherine Hess, Linda Komaroff, and George Saliba, eds., *The arts of fire: Islamic influences on glass and ceramics of the Italian Renaissance* (Los Angeles, Getty Publications, 2004), 19.

²⁷ Małgorzata Redlak, 'Syro-Egyptian underglaze painted ceramics from Kom El-Dikka 13th-15th century study report (2002/2003)', *Polish archaeology in the Mediterranean* (2003): 46-52, at 47.

²⁸ For a surviving stencil used in mural painting, dating to the medieval period, see Roger Rosewall, *Medieval Wall Paintings* (Bloomsbury Publishing, 2014), 130-131. A small stencil for painting ceramics was also found in an archaeological layer dating to the thirteenth or fourteenth centuries in Viljandi, Estonia and reported in Gitte Hansen, Steven P. Ashley, and Irene Baug, ed.s, *Everyday products in the middle ages: crafts, consumption and the individual in Northern Europe c. AD 800-1600* (Oxford, Oxbow books, 2015), 94.

The pinpointing of stencil use in drawings is a subtle new space for research. In contexts like mural painting, the task is less daunting; one can simply point to abrupt, piled-up edges on paint layers and the degree of consistency in the shape of repeated motifs.

²⁹ A rare textual acknowledgement of stencils is found in Cennini's *Libro dell'Arte*. The reference comes at the beginning of a section on the preparation of various glues. He says that '[glue] is also used sometimes when paper is to be glued together for making transfer patterns.' Bambach has interpreted the term Cennini uses (*istrafori*) to mean stencils (Bambach, *Drawing and painting in the Italian Renaissance workshop* (see note 24), 156). Of course, Cennini is likely referring to the bonding of multiple sheets at their edges to create a larger sheet. Cennini, *The Book of the Art* (see note 24), 88.

³⁰ For some papers attesting to the heterogeneous applications for drypoint, see: William Schipper, 'Dry-Point Compilation Notes in the Benedictional of St Æthelwold', *The British Library Journal* 20(1) (1994): 17-34; Carl F. Barnes Jr and Lon R. Shelby, L. R., 'The Preliminary Drawing for Villard de Honnecourt's' Sepulchre of a

Saracen', *Gesta* 25(1) (1986): 135-8; Philip G. Rusche, 'Dry-point glosses to Aldhelm's De laudibus virginittatis in Beinecke 401', *Anglo-Saxon England* 23 (1994): 195-213.

Metalpoint and silverpoint are frequently conflated, irrespective of the silver content of the markmaking tool. The term plummet may also be encountered, denoting a metallic writing implement with significant lead content and distinct from other metalpoints in its erasability and capacity to mark smoother surfaces. A good introduction to the material aspects of metalpoint may be found in Kristi Dahm, 'The stylus revealed: A metalpoint identification study of fifteenth- and sixteenth-century Italian drawings in the Metropolitan Museum of Art', *The Paper Conservator* 28(1) (2004): 75-86.

³¹ In theory, the use of a stencil for landmasses might be identified by noting nearly identical large, detailed islands in charts by one author, but with slightly variable placement relative to the mainland coasts. This possibility requires further investigation.

³² See Fig. 4.

³³ Signs of slipped stencils in mural painting are reported in Bambach, *Drawing and painting in the Italian Renaissance workshop* (see note 24), 156. I have noted several cases of doubled ink lines on extant nautical charts, but at present the interpretation of these lines is too ambiguous for inclusion in this text.

³⁴ Grouping charts into size categories based on the dimensions of their supports is inadequate for any argument that cartographic models fell into a few specific groups, because the production of new charts with fixed-scale copying methods produces groupings of set drawing size, not support size. Even if the supports for two charts present identical measurements, a difference of a centimeter (or even less) in the size of a drawing has serious implications for the method of copying we might infer. This is a point raised by Pujades, although he adopts a different strategy for capturing the size of drawings than I do. Pujades i Bataller, *Les cartes portolanes* (see note 1), 477-8.

³⁵ An analog version of the same procedure has long been used when studying 'fine art' paintings, using sheets of acetate. One advantage of tracing digitally is that it allows rescaling where needed.

³⁶ A more wide-ranging discussion of Benincasa that addresses the remarkable consistency seen in some aspects of his work may be consulted in Tony Campbell, 'The style and content of Grazioso Benincasa's charts: imitation, innovation and repetition', *Map History*, <<http://www.maphistory.info/benincasa.html>>. Accessed 1/9/2020.

³⁸ Metalpoint lines are usually pale and fine, but their color will depend on the composition and oxidation states of the constituent metals in the stylus. Drypoint marks generally look grayish or appear as a "highlight" on the parchment, depending on how the page is illuminated (a cursory search of 'pointe sèche' on Gallica (the digital archives of the Bibliothèque Nationale de France) returns numerous digitized drypoint-ruled manuscripts witnessing the variable photographic registry of this kind of mark).

³⁹ The traces of drypoint on this chart were noted by La Roncière-Mollat in 1984, quoted in Falchetta, *Marinai, mercanti, cartografi, pittori* (see note 7), 73.

⁴⁰ This point was made as early as the 1940s, when Leslie Weber Jones remarked on drypoint ruling that '[t]hose who have had to depend on facsimiles, however, may not always be aware of the real state of affairs.' Although the high-resolution color photographs help, they are no substitute for raking light. Leslie Webber Jones, 'Pricking manuscripts: the instruments and their significance', *Speculum* 21(4) (1946): 389-403, at 389.

William Schipper echoes this sentiment, observing that despite decades of scrutiny from art historians and paleographers, a series of drypoint notes in the margin of an important codex had gone unnoticed. The

scholar attributes this oversight to specialists' inattention to the (at first glance, blank) margins of the book's pages, a general lack of concern with the book-as-object, and the poor visibility of these drypoint markings on microfiche. Schipper, 'Dry-Point Compilation Notes in the Benedictional of St Æthelwold' (see note 30).

Visualizing drypoint marks is typically done in situ with raking light. Reflectance transformation imaging (RTI), developed by researchers at Hewlett-Packard Laboratories, is an exciting new method of recording the disposition of drypoint on manuscripts. A case study in the use of RTI can be found in: Bill Endres, *Digitizing Medieval Manuscripts: The St. Chad Gospels, Materiality, Recoveries, and Representation in 2D and 3D* (Leeds, Arc Humanities Press, 2019), chapter 2.

⁴¹ Bambach, *Drawing and painting in the Italian Renaissance workshop* (see note 24), 12.

⁴² Among other materials, artists used charcoal powder or lead white (suggested by Cennini), gesso, quicklime, pale pumice, *tuhong* (a red earth found on surviving Chinese medieval pricked patterns), burnt wine dregs, black chalk, sifted ashes, and ink. *Ibid.*, 76-77.

⁴³ *Ibid.*

⁴⁴ Pricked models for the painting of ceramics are discussed in Catherine Hess, *Maiolica in the making: the Gentili/Barnabei archive, vol. 4* (Los Angeles, Getty Publications, 1999). Although pounce dots have long been detected in mural paintings, the use of infrared reflectography has more recently provided numerous examples in easel paintings.

⁴⁵ Crescentio, *Nautica Mediterranea* (see note 23).

⁴⁶ 'Vous pouvez aussi piquer l'Estampe ou dessein que vous voulez peindre avec une pointe d'Aiguille fort fine, après [sic] quoy vous poserez votre Estampe ou dessein sur votre Veslin, & passerez pardessus la ponce qui se fait de charbon bien sec réduit en poudre, que l'on enferme dans un linge un peu fin, & vous vous servirez de la pointe d'argent pour marquer sur vostre Veslin tous les traits que vostre ponce aura formée, & ensuite d'une mie de pain que vous passerez doucement pardessus, pour empescher que vôtre Veslin ne soit noirci par cette poudre de charbon.' Catherine Perrot, *Les leçons royales, ou La manière de peindre en miniature les fleurs et les oyseaux ... composées par damoiselle Catherine Perrot* (Paris, Jean B. Nego, 1686): 5-6. A digitized copy of the book is accessible at <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k1041775q>.

⁴⁷ I selected at random a representative segment of the Perrino Vesconte atlas (Zentralbibliothek Zürich, R.P.4) showing the area between the boot of Italy and Sicily. I uploaded the image onto CorelDRAW® Home & Student (version 21.0.0.638) and placed dots on the coastlines, simulating pricking. I then rendered the 'model' layer invisible, and digitally connected the dots based on the pounce dots and a solid grasp of the line styles used by Perrino. Finally, I restored the visibility of the "model" layer and compared the results.

I began by testing what would happen if only headlands were pricked on the model. In this case, the model and copy would correspond on the position of the capes but show rather free variation on the bays in between them, and the density of pounce dots would be relatively low (approximately 6 dots/cm). A greater degree of overall concordance was reached by adding 'pounced dots' to the minima of bays (resulting in a density of 10 dots/cm; already on the high end of what is seen in fine art painting; Bambach, *Drawing and painting in the Italian Renaissance workshop* (see note 24), 57). Finally, I 'pricked' zealously, aiming at total correspondence. To achieve this correspondence on the selected segment of the chart required 19 dots/cm, a density that cannot have been feasible. Even in the case of obsessive pricking and pouncing, it is unlikely that one could go without visual reference to a model once offshore features are added into the mix.

⁴⁸ Pricked patterns were also used to copy the ships, cartouches, and even some of the calligraphic labels (such as the heading *Mer Noire*) decorating François Ollive's 1662 showpiece chart kept at the Bibliothèque Nationale

de France, call number GE SH ARCH-43. Partial reliance on pricked patterns may explain the otherwise puzzling difference in polish between these and other, clumsier ornamental figures on the chart. No pounce dots were detected on the (heavily overpainted) coastlines.

⁴⁹ Bambach, *Drawing and painting in the Italian Renaissance workshop* (see note 24), 12. I have not been able to find any satisfactory account of the origins of this copying method; it seems, however, to rely upon access to paper.

⁵⁰ Cortés, *Breve Compendio* (see note 3), fol. 63.

⁵¹ Sheehan, 'The Functions of Portolan Maps' (see note 2), 63-69.

⁵² I am not aware of documents giving the cost of graphite in the century after its discovery, but for cartographers based around the Mediterranean, graphite was a commodity imported at great distance. Carbon transfer is possible with a graphite-rubbed sheet, but wasting this material when lamp soot or charcoal could be used at for free is highly implausible.

⁵³ Ideally, one would execute several transfer drawings and direct drawings in period-appropriate media, varying and noting the amount of pressure and type of stylus used for the transfer drawing. The lines produced by each method could then be documented with macro photography and hand-held digital microscopy. This would provide a good basis for assigning preliminary lines on charts to the respective drawing methods.

⁵⁴ João Teixeira Albernaz may have been another user of this method, as seen in the atlas of 1640, especially the *Orbis Terrarum* (Bibliothèque Nationale de France, CPL GE FF-14409); the atlas of 1630, which presents puzzlingly extensive disconformities between the transfer drawing and final drawing (Library of Congress, G1015 .T4 1630); and the uncolored depiction of the Amazon (Bibliothèque Nationale de France, GE SH 18 PF 166 DIV 1 P 3 D).

Diogo Homem's probable use of the method stands in vivid contrast with Albernaz's: where Albernaz only loosely adheres to his preliminary drawing, Homem shows a remarkably meticulous effort to follow and conceal all signs of the drafting process. His 1561 atlas stored in the Austrian National Library (*Mappae nauticae* 14 Cod 335) offers glimpses of a meticulously-executed carbon transfer; see in particular on the uncolored transfer drawings of coastlines extending beyond the gilt border on the left side of the chart depicting Florida and the northern coasts of South America. Similar hints may be noted on the atlas of 1574, especially on the coast adjacent to Alexandretta on the chart covering the Peloponnese to the Near East (Bibliothèque Nationale de France, CPL GE DD-2006).

Finally, the atlas of Vesconte Maggiolo of 1511 (John Carter Brown Library, 3-Size Codex z 2) shows what appears to be a carbon transfer drawing based on the color and quality of the preliminary lines; in some of the charts, this drawing is obvious and extensive. As with other authors, liberties are taken when inking the transferred design for inlets and rivers; one characteristic aspect of Maggiolo may be his rendering of these banks as straight, parallel lines in the preliminary drawing, and later giving them sinuous contours in ink. That it is a transfer drawing, rather than a preparatory sketch, is suggested by the way the mountains are limned in the polar projection of the northern hemisphere; the outer perimeters of entire "stacks" of simplified mountains are sometimes rendered without internal contours. This would be a natural shortcut in the creation of a transfer drawing, but a very odd way of sketching. Marks of probable carbon transfer are also plentiful on the chart of the Aegean Sea. The atlas may have relied on at least two sorts of preliminary drawing: carbon transfer, and direct sketching (seen, for instance, on the label in scrollwork reading "mare meridionalis" on the polar projection chart). That Maggiolo troubled himself to jot down the text to be entered in a label such as this is unusual.

⁵⁵ It is likely that Agnese inked these 'x's in one fell swoop and without rotating the page; they are overwhelmingly orientated at about the same angle, which we might not expect if he alternated inking coastlines and hazards.

⁵⁶ Christopher Scheiner, *Pantographice, seu, Ars dileandi [...]* (Rome, Ludovico Grignano, 1631). The full text has been digitized and is freely accessible on archive.org. A translation of part of the first chapter into English can be consulted in William Wallace, 'XIX. Account of the Invention of the Pantograph, and a Description of the Eidograph, a Copying Instrument invented by William Wallace, AM, FRS Edin., FRAS, Memb. Cam. Phil. Soc., &c., Professor of Mathematics in the University of Edinburgh', *Earth and Environmental Science Transactions of The Royal Society of Edinburgh* 13(2) (1836): 418-39.

⁵⁷ Mario Biagioli, 'From print to patents: Living on instruments in early modern Europe', *History of Science* 44(2) (2006): 139-86.

⁵⁸ A pantograph for drawing based on interlocking cogs was devised and described by Hero of Alexandria; Scheiner was surely familiar with his works. The implication in Scheiner's account that there is more than one way to make a pantograph meeting the same basic functional criteria may be read as an inside-joke to mathematicians among his audience. There is no indication that Hero's pantograph was ever used by medieval or early modern chartmakers, or widely-known among artists.

⁵⁹ Indeed, the character of Georgius urges our protagonist Scheiner *not* to speak too freely of his marvelous construction, but to share his invention in particular with the Spanish, to somehow aid in missionary efforts (Scheiner, *ibid.*, 6).

⁶⁰ The circumstances surrounding the discovery of a graphite mine in Cumberland in the early sixteenth century are nebulous. By the late 1500s, graphite was a familiar writing material in several European countries, among them Italy and Switzerland. Its rapid adoption suggests that graphite provided characteristics hitherto lacking in the tools used by artisans. Eric H. Voice provides an excellent overview of the manufacture of graphite pencils. His article includes a reference to the *Epicoene*, an English play of 1609 in which graphite is specifically cited as a character's preferred material for drawing maps. Eric H. Voice, 'The History of the Manufacture of Pencils', *Transactions of the Newcomen Society* 27(1) (1949): 131-41.

⁶¹ Graphite is relatively soft, erasable, and non-friable, which makes it a perfect material for work with a pantograph.

⁶² If the pantograph were merely used, like the grid, to create a new workshop model at a new scale, which was subsequently copied using another bridging technique, the existence or nonexistence of graphite lingering on a copy would be irrelevant.

⁶³ Monsaingeon, 'Quelques observations (de beotien) sur la carte muette & enigmatique de Baldasaro da Maïolo Vesconte [Gênes], 1589' (see note 9).

⁶⁴ Chaves is discussing the point-by-point construction of a new chart, and remarks that '[...] es necessario tener muy copioso y verdadero trasunto de pintura, o escritura, o relación donde se puda sacar, ahora sea escritura, así como Ptolemeo u otro alguno que lo trate, o relación de vista y experiencia que lo declare.' Cortés prefaces his description of carbon transfer with the counsel '[...] han se de procurar los mas aprobados y verdaderos [padrones] que se hallen [...]' (Cortés, *Breve Compendio* (see note 3), fol. 63r). While Cortés suggests that a chartmaker might avail themselves of lists of latitudes, he does not specify how one might resolve any non-conformities between these two sources of information (i.e. a model chart and collection of coordinates).

⁶⁵ See endnote 54 regarding Maggiolo's treatment of rivers and inlets, for example.